

Realisation of a carbon negative combustor for gas turbines

Gas turbines can be converted to carbon negative technologies using biomass energy combined with carbon capture and storage processes

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Gas turbine sector evolution

The power sector is undergoing rapid technological change. It is likely that conventional gas turbines will need to be integrated in systems employing biofuels and/or carbon capture usage and storage (CCUS) at competitive costs. The EU is moving swiftly towards low carbon technologies (such as energy efficiency, smart grids, renewables and CCUS) under the European Energy Union Strategy (European Commission, 2015). The development of carbon sequestration methods was identified by the US National Academy of Engineering ((NAE, 2017) as one of the 'Grand Challenges for Engineering'. This technology was considered of paramount importance for the UN Sustainable Development Goals, SDG7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), and SDG5 (Climate Action). The Gas Turbine Chemical Looping Combustor for Carbon Negative Power Generation (GTCLC-NEG) project addresses two of the five pillars of the European Energy Union Strategy – renewable energy and CCUS – and couples these with breakthrough technologies, such as chemical looping combustion (CLC).

Biomass absorbs CO_2 during growth and releases it when burnt, but if the CO_2 is captured after combustion, this will result in a net flow of carbon out of the atmosphere. Thus, when bioenergy is coupled to CCUS, it is called bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS), which according to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) report of 2014 is a negative emission technology (NET) (IPCC, 2014). This means that BECCS is able to remove CO_2 by the atmosphere.

One of the most effective ways to couple biomass energy and CCUS is to burn biomass or biofuels (i.e. pyrolysis oils, biogas, and solid biomass) in a chemical looping combustor, where CO_2 can be easily captured after exiting the fuel reactor (see **Figure 1**). CLC uses an oxygen carrier based on a metal oxide to transfer oxygen to the fuel and obtains CO_2 in pure form inherently in the process. As CLC is not burdened with any separation work, it is particularly applicable for carbon capture and can achieve negative emissions when used with biomass. The social and economic impact of substituting current natural gas combined cycle power plants with GTCLC cycles is huge. In a study presented at the SDEWES Conference in 2020, we calculated that this project could be covered in part by the increasing carbon credit price and could generate at least 100,000 new jobs on a European level, solving a key problem for the gas turbine sector.

Figure 1 Chemical looping combustion technology

GTCLC-NEG concept

As well as being awarded a Marie Curie - Individual Fellowship, the GTCLC-NEG project has been funded by the European Commission (EU Horizon 2020 Framework Programme, Grant 101018576), with the Spanish National

Research Council (CSIC) as the host institution. The GTCLC-NEG project is being developed at Instituto de Carboquímica (ICB-CSIC, see Figure 2) from July 2021 to June 2023.

The aim of the project is to promote a carbon negative technology capable of burning multiple biofuels derived from biomass and to capture the CO₂ emissions at a very low cost. In this way, there will be negative GHG emissions due to the use of BECCS, a technology that is set to be developed by 2050 according to the IPCC.

The proposed plant is based on the coupling of a chemical looping combustor to a gas turbine, as proposed in Figure 3.

As it can be seen in the proposed plant, the compressed air used to oxidise the oxygen carrier is heated in the air reactor and then heated in the air expanded in a gas turbine to produce electricity. In the fuel reactor, biofuels (in this case, pyrolysis oils) are used to reduce the oxygen carrier.

Possible technical barriers include:

- ① Suitable metal oxides or bimetallic oxygen carriers are needed
- ② Low attrition rate oxygen carriers that can work in extreme conditions are required

Figure 2 Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), Instituto de Carboquímica, Zaragoza, Spain

- ③ Kinetics aspects under high pressure and temperature conditions are unknown
- ④ Reactor injection system must be adapted to biofuels
- ⑤ The use of the hot air produced from the air reactor in a gas turbine has to be optimised; exhausts should be filtered to retain the dust released by oxygen carrier attrition
- ⑥ High electrical efficiency of the power system has to be granted together with high fuel conversion in the combustor.

To summarise, one of the most critical aspects of the technology is the operation of the chemical looping combustor at high pressures. Rarely

Figure 3 GTCLC-NEG concept

What is Horizon Europe?

Horizon 2020 was the EU Research and Innovation programme with nearly \$80 billion of funding over the period 2014-2020. Many of the projects funded by Horizon 2020 are ongoing.

Horizon Europe is the latest EU funding programme for research and innovation, with a budget of €95.5 billion over the period 2021-2027. It tackles climate change, helps to achieve the UN's Sustainable Development Goals, and boosts the EU's competitiveness and growth.

The programme facilitates collaboration and strengthens the impact of research and innovation in developing, supporting, and implementing EU policies while tackling global challenges. It supports creating and better dispersing of excellent knowledge and technologies. Legal entities from the EU and associated countries can participate.

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has this been done on a large scale, and for this reason the modelling of the reactor and the chemical processes that occur during pressurised CLC appear to be of scientific interest.

Effective models have already been developed at zero-dimensional level at the Instituto de Carboquímica, based on the shrinking core model (SCM), which is widely adopted in literature to describe oxygen carrier behaviour. Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) models have also been developed. Nevertheless, the effect of pressure on the CLC process has not yet been fully described.

The GTCLC-NEG project aims to apply different strategies, which can be found in the literature, to model the fuel and air reactors using CFD software, with improved kinetic constants. Once the CFD model has been tested on plants available at the Instituto de Carboquímica, the data available will be used to design the final combustor and couple it to a gas turbine in Aspen Plus software. The mass and energy balances of the complete plant will then be verified by the proprietary software of an important gas turbine production company.

Project objectives

The main objective of the current project is to develop a new combustor capable of burning multiple biofuels derived from biomass (such as pyrolysis oil, biogas, and syngas) and to capture the CO₂ emissions at a very low cost.

The development process will be efficient and cheap, and it will be possible to integrate it in a power plant with negative CO₂ emissions. This will be done by overcoming current barriers through proper training.

The following objectives will be developed by the project work packages:

- 1 Production of four innovative bimetallic oxygen carriers and characterisation of their performance at high pressures and high temperatures
- 2 Realisation of tests of CLC of three biofuels (pyrolysis oils, syngas, and biogas) in high pressure (1-1.5 MPa) and high temperature (1200-1300°C) batch fluidised bed reactor. Attrition and agglomeration issues will be assessed
- 3 Development of:
 - Particle model, where the main kinetics aspects of redox reactions is analysed in critical conditions
 - Zero-dimensional model of the CLC reactor
 - Scaled-up model in Aspen Plus of the GTCLC plant
- 4 Realisation of tests with the best-performing oxygen carrier in a recirculated multifuel 1 kW CLC unit fluidised bed reactor, optimising the reactor injection and hot exhaust gas cleaning, to obtaining carbon conversion of >95% and CO₂ output of >90%.
- 5 Preparation of guidelines and an exploitation plan for the design of chemical looping combustors to be used with gas turbines; development of a system study in collaboration with an important gas turbines production company on the integration of the proposed CLC reactor into a power generation unit. Final optimisation of the plant's technical and economic performance should lead to an electricity cost of less than 100 €/MWh and an electrical efficiency of higher than 50%. This will end up with GTCLC plant design guidelines.

Project work packages

Work package 1 (WP1) involves a state-of-the-art review of the performance of oxygen carriers and a database will also be realised. This will report the physical chemical characteristics of the most commonly used oxygen carriers and also their kinetics characteristics, where available. Fe, Ni, Mn will be taken into consideration to realise the commercially available oxygen carriers. Also, different supports for the metals will be taken into consideration. Oxygen carriers will then be prepared and characterised, aiming at the development of materials that give high performance in CLC tests at high temperatures and high pressures. The preparation methods to be tested are impregnation, mechanical mixing, and granulation. The characterisation of oxygen carriers will be done through pressurised PTGA, X-ray diffraction, BET, and SEM.

In WP2, the prepared oxygen carriers will be screened using batch fluidised bed reactors. Three repetitions of each test will be performed using model compounds for the reduction reactions in the fuel reactor (phenol, acetic acid, toluene, experimentally simulated syngas, experimentally simulated biogas). 500g of oxygen carrier will be used in each test – 300g for hot conditions tests and 200g for attrition tests). The screening will be based on batch fluidised beds. Evolved gas analysis (EGA) will be performed from the batch plants.

WP3 involves the development of models. Data obtained from WP1 will be used to develop the particle model. This will be done through curve fitting, using models already employed for fuels behaviour, but also metal and support behaviour. The main phenomena that will be considered are diffusion and the kinetics of chemical reactions. The kinetic model will be inserted in a more comprehensive zero-dimensional reactor model, building on the 20-plus years of experience at the Instituto de Carboquímica.

In the zero-dimensional models, both oxygen carrier and biofuel behaviour will be modelled. Detail of the models will reach atomical and molecular levels using density functional theory and molecular dynamics models. Attention will be focused on the behaviour of oxygen vacancies in the oxygen carriers and their effects on its reactivity. Results of the model will be calibrated with the EGA data. The mass and energy balances obtained from the

experimental campaigns in WP2 will then be scaled up. Finally, an Aspen Plus model will be implemented to simulate the GTCLC plant. Production of biofuels and the kinetics of the reactor will also be integrated in the Aspen model. Mass and energy balances and economic analysis of the entire plant will be performed too. Final data will be used to perform a life-cycle assessment (LCA).

In WP4, biofuels will be processed in a 1 kW continuous recirculating fluidised bed. About 3kg of oxygen carrier will be used for each test. So only the best oxygen carrier, determined through the experiments in WP1 and WP2 and the models developed in WP3, will be chosen. Particular attention will be placed on biofuel injection and exhaust gas cleaning. Guidelines on how to design fluidised bed reactors for GTCLC will also be drafted in collaboration with Tampere University. The mass balances calculated by the zero-dimensional model developed in WP3 will be further checked against the experimental tests performed in the continuous CLC reactor. The model will also be used to optimise the performances of the continuous reactors, focusing on optimal inventory management, maximum carbon conversion, reduction of attrition, and exhaust gas cleaning.

In WP5, a model of the CLC combustor fed with biofuels will be integrated with a gas turbine. Technical analysis will be performed using industrial models, to optimise turbine working conditions using hot air, instead of exhaust combustion gases. Guidelines for the design of GTCLC combustors and an exploitation plan on how to develop a prototype of the combustor will be developed in collaboration with industrial partners. Particular attention will be given to heat integration, combustor efficiency, and entire plant electrical efficiency, as well as plant total investment costs. CO₂ concentration in the exhaust will also be optimised.

VIEW REFERENCES

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